

RELATED STUDIES ON CHILD FRIENDLY SCHOOL-HEALTH ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: According to Murtaza (2011), a ‘Child Friendly School’ is a school that recognizes and nurtures the achievement of children's basic rights. Child Friendly Schools work with all commitment-holders, especially parents/guardians of students. It values the many kinds of contributions they can make in the development of a learning environment for children according to the children's current and future needs. The learning environments of Child Friendly Schools are characterized by equity, balance, freedom, solidarity, non-violence, and a concern for physical, mental, and emotional health. These lead to the development of knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, morals so that children can live together in a harmonious way. This paper is a review of a set of ‘Related Studies on Child Friendly School-Health Environment.’ A synthesis of which, was then generated.

Keywords: Child Friendly Environment: Child Friendly School: Environment: Health: Health Environment: Synthesis.

I. INTRODUCTION

On September 20, 2021, the Department of Education (DepEd) announced that President Rodrigo Roa Duterte has approved the pilot implementation of limited face-to-face classes in Covid-19 low-risk areas (DepEd, 2021). That in effect, partially lifts, or easing the strict quarantine measures to contain the spread of the COVID-19, which, the Philippine government imposed on March 16, 2020 (Manila Bulletin, 2021). This policy was implemented in schools in the different parts of the country, especially those located in areas with low risk of COVID 19 infections, as per Inter-Agency Task Force (AITF) Alert Level Metrics (Freeman, 2021).

The operational guidelines on the pilot implementation of the limited face-to-face learning modality prepared by DOH and DepEd with the support of the World Health Organization (WHO), the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF), provide health and safety standards, and that their main concern focuses on children’s health (DepEd, 2021). That is, as defined in the Constitution of the World Health Organization (WHO, 1948) as cited by Svalastog, Donev, Kristoffersen and Gajović (2017), health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity.

As a guide for the health-related assessment, the ‘Child Friendly School (CFS) Model’, laid out by UNICEF and adopted by DepEd, will be appropriate to utilize. The Child-Friendly School System Model has seven indicators which include children’s health and well-being, and safe and protective spaces for children, which are dimensions of the school health environment (UNICEF, 2006).

“Child friendly environment aims to develop a learning environment in which children are motivated and able to learn. Staff members are friendly and welcoming to children and attend to all their health and safety needs” (Yunus, 2003). Mustard (2002) posit that children can get all their needed skills when they have a friendly environment in their school and the teachers can only create this environment if they are competent and knowledgeable. Environment-enhancing

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strategies include policies to provide a non-discriminatory safe and secure environment, skills-based health education, provision of health and other services, effective referral to external health service providers and links with the community should be put in place.

This review of related studies will generate a greater comprehension about ‘Child Friendly School-Health Environment,’ which will give the researcher a firm grasp of the different essential components of research, promoting deeper insights thereof.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE**PURPOSE OF THE STUDY**

The purpose of this paper was to principally describe the completed researches on ‘Child Friendly School-Health Environment.’

RELATED STUDIES**Creating a Friendly School Learning Environment**

The study of Oluremi, O. F. (2021) on “Creating a Friendly School Learning Environment“, evaluated the school learning environment in Nigerian’s primary schools. Areas of study include, classroom environment, provision of infrastructural facilities, Teacher/Pupils interaction in the classroom setting. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used, questionnaire tagged (CFV) “Child friendly environment was the instrument used to elicit information from the respondents. The population of the study consisted of all the teachers in the public primary schools in Osun State Nigeria. Sample comprised 250 teachers from selected Secondary Schools in the state. Data were collected using frequency counts means and percentages. Results showed that 25% of the selected schools were not child friendly. This was because they lacked infrastructural facilities such as toilet facilities, chairs, desks and tables. Most classrooms were not friendly to pupils with disabilities.

Based on the findings, it was recommended that all education stakeholders in the primary education sector should made classroom environment attractive and pleasant for pupils. This would enhance teaching and learning and improve teacher productivity

Provision of Health Facilities for Promoting Healthy Child-Friendly School Environment

The study of Ofojebe, W. N., and Ezugoh, T. C. (2020) on the “Provision of Health Facilities for Promoting Healthy Child-Friendly School Environment” is an investigation of the provision of health facilities for promoting a healthy child friendly school environment in primary schools in Delta State. Four research questions guided the study. The descriptive survey research design was employed in the study. The population comprised 1,132 primary school teachers in the public primary schools in Delta State. Sample of the study consisted 566 public primary school head teachers drawn from the entire head teachers at 50% using the proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was a questionnaire personally developed by the researchers, titled: “Healthy Child Friendly School Environment Questionnaire (HCFSEQ)” containing 31 items. The research instrument was validated by three experts in Educational Management and Policy Department and the reliability of the instrument was ascertained through a pilot-test by sampling 20 head teachers from 20 public primary schools in Anambra State. Data collected were analyzed using mean scores and standard deviation to answer the research questions.

The findings of this study revealed among others that there were no adequate provisions for school health facilities as regards to the provisions of school clinics, sanitary, sports and recreational health facilities for promoting a healthy child friendly school environment in primary schools in Delta State. From the findings of the study, recommendations were also proffered and among them include that: Delta State Government in collaboration with the Delta State Universal Basic Education (DSUBE) should make adequate provision for health facilities like school clinics, sanitary, sports and recreational health facilities for promoting a healthy child friendly school environment in primary schools in Delta State.

Assessment of Child - Friendly Environment in Public Schools

A Child-Friendly School is a school that recognizes and nurtures the achievements of children’s basic rights. A school is considered “Child Friendly” when it provides a safe, clean, healthy, and protective environment for children. The study of Saleem, A., Shaheen, I., and Zahid, H. (2020) “Assessment of Child - Friendly Environment in Public Schools“, was mainly

aimed to assess the basic needs of the children in the public school, to analyze the behavior of the staff with parents and children, and to analyze the availability of child-friendly facilities in the public schools.

The study was descriptive and it was conducted to an analysis of facilities provided by the government for Child-Friendly Schools. The target population was public sector schools of the Multan district. A convenient sampling technique was utilized for the selection of the sample which comprises 81 respondents (male 40 and female 41). For the collection of data, a questionnaire was utilized in this study. With the help of the survey technique, data had been collected from participants. Collected data were analyzed in terms of descriptive statistics (frequency distribution, mean, and percentage).

Significant findings exposed that schools are providing maximum of the facilities such as clean drinking water, security system for the school, enough classroom with proper lights, attendance register for students, refer children to get treatment for their health problem, parent-teacher meeting, etc. Major recommendations for this study were; schools should introduce committees to stop bullying and corporal punishment in their schools and coordinate with a local organization to survey so that all children can come to schools.

Child-Friendly School Environment: A Case Study

The study of Tripathi, K. P. (2020) "Child-Friendly School Environment: A Case Study", was carried out to investigate the status of child-friendly school environment, and identify school's policy towards it. It was delimited to Pokhara Metropolitan of Kaski District. To accomplish the objectives, the explanatory sequential research design was used. The survey technique was used for quantitative and observation was used to qualitative study. There were 128 basic community schools. Eleven schools were selected randomly. The interview schedule and observation checklist were the major tools of data collection. Collected data and information were analyzed both quantitatively as well as qualitatively as per their nature in the table. The findings of the study demonstrated that physical facilities in community schools in Pokhara Metropolitan City seem satisfactory. The researcher asked and observed the school sites. More than one quarter schools (27.3%) had peace and quiet place to teach. More than one-third school (36.4%) had satisfactory and the same (36.4%) had no open and enough space. The study also found that all schools had little raised and dry land and not to risk of sinking during the monsoon. More than half of the schools (54.5%) had the satisfactory situation on sufficient space and on adequate water and facility of waste disposal. From the observation, it was found that nearly two third schools had poor situation of restrooms without water and latches. It is concluded that the community schools tried their best to make child-friendly school environment, but those attempts were found to be insufficient. The study recommended that communication, cooperation, and coordination are needed among the stakeholders to plan for the quality education in schools.

Teachers' Perception on School Health Services

Teaching health and physical education by qualified teachers can support the promotion of health among school children. In Nepal, school health program has not been run effectively as health and any subject teachers teach physical education subject. On the other hand, government policy makers and school management does not seem serious about this issue. In this context, the study of Poudel, A. P. (2018) on "Teachers' Perception on School Health Services" intends to explore perceptions of teachers on students' health promotion through school health services. The study was based on qualitative research design specifically phenomenological approach. Qualitative data were collected from twelve purposefully selected teachers of six different community schools of Kathmandu using in-depth interview technique. The collected data were analyzed by applying thematic approach. The study collected perception of Health and Physical Education (HPE) teachers regarding school health services, health promoting activities, water, sanitation and hygiene that play crucial role to promote healthy behavior of students. In their perception, school health services should be provided to promote students' health, control the epidemics and communicable diseases and to create healthy school environment. In their perception, child friendly school creates an open-learning environment and keeps students mentally sound, creative and well-motivated in learning. Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that teachers' perception on school health program is fairly satisfactory. However, their health activities are limited within the classroom practices and theoretical notions included in the textbook.

Healthy School Environment: Effectiveness of Hand Washing Instruction in an Elementary School Setting

Hand washing remains the single most important action for preventing the spread of infectious diseases. Although easy and inexpensive, promoting hand hygiene in an elementary school can be a challenge. The study of Celik, L. A., and Pancoe, D. L. (2012), "Healthy School Environment: Effectiveness of Hand Washing Instruction in an Elementary School Setting"

was a collaborative project between the co-investigators (a registered nurse at an urban elementary school and a senior high school student working on a senior International Baccalaureate research project), the 5th-grade science teacher, and a physician from the local children's hospital. The study was to (a) determine the effectiveness of a 30-minute hand washing educational intervention at decreasing organisms on the hands of 5th-grade students and (b) introduce the 5th-grade students to the scientific method. Forty-one percent of the 5th-grade students used an effective hand washing technique after receiving instruction on proper hand washing.

III. A SYNTHESIS

As to objectives, the studies of: Oluremi, O. F. (2021) on "Creating a Friendly School Learning Environment", evaluated the school learning environment in Nigerian's primary schools, in terms of the classroom environment, provision of infrastructural facilities, Teacher/Pupils interaction in the classroom setting; Ofojebe, W. N., and Ezugoh, T. C. (2020) on the "Provision of Health Facilities for Promoting Healthy Child-Friendly School Environment" investigated the provision of health facilities for promoting a healthy child friendly school environment in primary schools; Saleem, A., Shaheen, I., and Zahid, H. (2020) on "Assessment of Child - Friendly Environment in Public Schools", mainly aimed to assess the basic needs of the children in the public school, to analyze the behavior of the staff with parents and children, and to analyze the availability of child-friendly facilities in the public schools; Tripathi, K. P. (2020) on "Child-Friendly School Environment: A Case Study", was carried out to investigate the status of child-friendly school environment, and identify school's policy towards it; Poudel, A. P. (2018) on "Teachers' Perception on School Health Services" explored perceptions of teachers on students' health promotion through school health services; and Celik, L. A., and Pancoe, D. L. (2012), on "Healthy School Environment: Effectiveness of Hand Washing Instruction in an Elementary School Setting" determined the effectiveness of a 30-minute hand washing educational intervention at decreasing organisms on the hands of 5th-grade students.

In terms of the subjects, the studies by Oluremi, O. F. (2021); and Ofojebe, W. N., and Ezugoh, T. C. (2020), had primary school teachers as their subjects. The rest of the related studies had as subjects, school staff with parents and children, personnel of the community schools, Health, and Physical Education (HPE) teachers, and 5th-grade students.

As to research design, the descriptive research design was adopted by: Oluremi, O. F. (2021); Ofojebe, W. N., and Ezugoh, T. C. (2020), and Saleem, A., Shaheen, I., and Zahid, H. (2020). Different research designs were adopted in the other studies as follows: Tripathi, K. P. (2020) used the explanatory sequential research design, in which the survey technique was used for quantitative and observation was used to qualitative study; Poudel, A. P. (2018) adopted the qualitative research design, specifically the phenomenological approach; and Celik, L. A., and Pancoe, D. L. (2012) which experimented on the effective hand washing technique.

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